

<p>ROLE OF TECHNOLOGY TO TEACH SPEAKING SKILLS IN HSC LEVEL STUDENTS IN BANGLADESH</p>		<p>Linguistics</p> <p>Keywords: Technology, teaching tactics, Projector, Spoken English, Facebook.</p>
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<p>Abstract</p> <p>The article explores the method of teaching speaking skills in the situation of English as a foreign language with the best use of technology for the higher secondary level students in Bangladesh. It also recommends the teachers regarding the techniques of teaching spoken English to the Bangladeshi EFL students using technology. The efficiency and difficulties of using technology have also been represented in this research. Forty teachers of six reputed colleges of Dhaka are interviewed as well as four questions are asked to the students about the lack of ability of spoken English. After the investigation it can be said indubitably that using technology in teaching spoken English to the higher secondary level learners is more efficient than any other levels. Presently, most of the learners are using smart phone, computer, laptop etc. and they are passing enormous time. When they will get the prospect of learning English, they will contemplate on it very effortlessly. The majority of the teachers and students are agreed to use technology for spoken English. Very few teachers and students are opposed about it reason is that they are not well trained of utilizing technology as well as they told if they are trained to use technology, they are keen to use computer as well as laptop in the classroom.</p>

1. INTRODUCTION

English is not a subject like international studies or spiritual studies. Rather it has some skills to be mastered by its learners. Still, most of the students of higher secondary level do not have the least capability to speak English though they read English regularly as an academic course. The current study may help the students in learning EFL speaking through the proper utilization of technology. This study explores the possible facts for the students of higher secondary level to master EFL speaking skill in a credible way. Technology has a significant role to play to enhance English language teaching and learning at the intermediate level but most of the teachers fell in problems using technology to teach speaking to the EFL learners. In addition, the teachers don't know the use of technology for example: projector, slides, laptop, sound systems etc. A lot of teachers consider that tablets and smart phones, through internet connection and messenger, can simply be a resource of interruption for learners as opposite to a learning instrument. It may be complicated for an educator to observe his learners so intimately in class as to decide whether they are using instructive apps on their smart phones or browsing Facebook, playing games or watching videos. It must be decided by the teacher whether or not to use filtered browsing on the equipments to cutting down on interruptions, that must not be a choice of the students' owns the device. The writing may help the teachers in language teaching and the reader will know about the devices of language teaching and learning. Generally, the English classes of intermediate level are separated into two different parts– English first paper and second paper. In English 1st paper, reading passages and different sorts of questions e.g. table, MCQ, rearranging, gap fillings are usually taught. The 2nd part is about grammar and grammatical parts e.g. articles,

prepositions, right forms of verbs, transformation of sentences are taught but they are not taught anything for developing their EFL speaking skill. Only theoretical knowledge can't make a person adroit in using any language.

2. OBJECTIVES

The objective of the study is to identify the teachers' problems and errors in teaching EFL speaking to the intermediate level students by using technology as well as to find out the solution to teach spoken English very easily.

3. LITERATURE REVIEW

In learning English, Speaking is one of the most important of four skills that must be mastered by students. Teaching method and using instruments are most important in language learning. The demand of English language for communication is beggar description (Sharma, 2009). The effect of technology has become huge in teaching and learning the language in addition to the instructor's role. In other words, the role of the instructor together with the role of the technology can lead to advanced learning results.

According to Lacina (2004), also cited in Lin (2009), if the teachers are looking for a way to add excitement to lessons and connect with more of the students then technology can be a solution for that. Combining and utilizing graphics, audio and videos can be addressed many styles of learning in a more successful technique and be an incredible support to the learners of English language. The verdict a way to introduce technology in teaching not only helps English language students' acquire a second language, but also improves inspiration and self-confidence.

According to Amin, M. (2019), teachers must well understand the limitations of the technologies while at the same time taking advantage of them. From a listening perspective, assuming the goal set by the teachers is to ensure the students are able to comprehend the natural speech of the natives and other fluent speakers of the language in question, various resources can be used, Vimeo and YouTube can be included but not limited to them, who have a extensive range of videos and audios in spoken speech, for a wide array of languages and dialects. Such resources can confirm to be helpful in preparing the spoken speech

According to Liaw (1997), teachers should offer English language learners a language-rich environment in which students are constantly engaged in language activities. Children need to be able to interact with each other so that learning through communication can occur. Computers can facilitate this type of environment. The computer can act as a tool to increase verbal exchange. The current study indeed focuses on the similar issues to facilitate teaching and learning of EFL speaking.

Eaton (2010) found that computer-based communication is a beneficial feature for language learning. Computer-assisted discussion intends to feature more equal participation than

face to-face discussion. Teachers or a few outspoken students are less likely to dominate the floor, resulting in class discussions that are more collaborative.

Amin, R. and et, al (2018) found that the teacher could frankly commence the issue but the use of the pictures help the teacher to bring out thoughts from the pupils and conduct them to the discussion as well as conversations. Therefore, the learners had plans of the topic earlier and help to develop their speaking abilities. In the undergraduate program, the teacher delivered a motivational video through the multimedia projector.

Zhao (2013) carried the analysis by stating that exposure and access to connecting, genuine, and understandable until now demanding resources in the target language is important for effective language learning. Hennessy (2005) also note down the introduction of ICT could act as a technique in inspiring teachers and students to work in new ways. Teacher-student and peer conversation, investigation, indication and analysis, questioning, and feedback differentiate these. Hennessy also sorted out that as learners become more independent, teachers think that they should encourage and support students in performing and thinking independently in order to gather spoken English.

4. METHODOLOGY

The researcher started the enquiry by determining all of the technologies that the different instructors use outside and inside of the classroom. The study was surveyed to identify the problems as well as the solutions of teaching and learning a language by using technology. The researcher took interview of 20 teachers of six renowned colleges of Dhaka city to find out the reasons of the students' being unable to speak English. The teacher respondents were interviewed to get the logical explanation about the problems of their students to speak English. A short questionnaire was served among the respondents to collect data.

5. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

The study report has presented the situation of the current use of technology in teaching EFL speaking skill. Teacher's Demographic profile and question answers are given. Table, column and pie charts are used to show percentage of the result.

The instructors use computers with internet access, projectors, simple sound systems, and microphones in the classrooms and deliver lectures. These tools are provided to the instructors in order to reduce the strain on the lecturers and improve their lessons and their interactions with the students. The instructors generally use these tools to assist them in their lectures and to provide visual aids to support the content of the lectures. On the other hand, the student will have smart phone with software. PowerPoint presentations are a preferred technology used for teaching because they integrate text, visuals, and audio, providing a useful setup to convey information.

Some instructors are using additional sources and platforms such as YouTube, an online video sharing website, to further improve their lectures, an open source learning platform, to

improve the course overall by providing additional content and support for the students to reference.

One of the major problems the lecturers needed to tackle was the lack of motivation and interest in the subject among the students. In order to keep the students interested and attentive, the instructors would try to integrate different kinds of media into their pedagogical methods. Some of the teachers turned to YouTube as a source of additional content for their classes. Some instructors would use videos of songs found on YouTube during class time in order to keep the students engaged and exercising their listening skills. Other teachers asked the students to use YouTube to practice their speaking skills by listening to different videos and then repeating what the video said. This simple exercise aims to improve the student’s pronunciation and fluency in speech. For this to work, the instructors generally use informative documentary videos, which the students would have no trouble understanding. In these situations, the instructors were using YouTube as a platform to find more content and create more diversity in the media used in their teaching methods. As well as the students may use software to practice grammar of their mobile phones. Use of education technology has grown in recent years, though common tools like laptops have not at all been universally adopted. According to a survey sponsored by Sprint Business, 60% of teachers use laptops in the classroom on a daily basis, while 58.7% report daily use of other education technology tools (Flexible Learning Strategies, 2017).

5.1. Report of Teacher’s Questionnaire

The opinion the experienced teacher-participants about teaching EFL speaking are given here. They are academically qualified with an MA in English or in ELT. Both male and female were considered in the study. Following statistics shows the results as given below:

SL	Statements	Number of Teachers	Options	Answers	Percentage
1	I use technology for teaching EFL speaking	40	Yes	26	65%
			No	14	35%
2	Through technology in teaching spoken English is easier than other ways	40	Agree	30	75%
			Disagree	10	25%
3	For learning spoken English listening to mp3 player is imperative	40	Yes	24	60%
			No	16	40%
4	I have taken training on technology for teaching EFL speaking	40	Yes	16	40%
			No	24	60%
5	I encourage the students to use technology for improving EFL speaking	40	Yes	40	100%
			No	00	00%
6	Only technology is enough for teaching speaking to the learners	40	Yes	12	30%
			No	28	70%

In the first statement, it is found that 65% teachers answered affirmative and 35% teachers replied ‘No’ about their use of technology in teaching EFL speaking. In the direct interview, they added that they are eager to use technology but they can’t get scopes for many reasons. If they get opportunity to use technology for teaching, they may use. In the second statement, teachers (75%) agreed that using technology in the class for teaching spoken English is easier than other ways. These teachers opined that using technology is very effective because most of the students are attracted by mobile, computer, laptop, TV, radio etc. If the devices are used for learning and teaching the students will be able to contribute more time for learning. 25% teachers disagreed about using technology. They think that using technology is easier but not easier than other ways. They argue that without technology can be learn or teach spoken English. They also sheared that practical teaching and learning in the class is more effective than other ways. In the third statement, it is found that 60% teachers support that listening to mp3 is imperative for learning English. They think that listening is the precondition for learning a language. 40% teachers said that listening is important but not most important. In statement 4, the report expresses that most of the teachers did not take training on technology for teaching EFL speaking. 60% teachers said that they could not get opportunity but they express their eagerness to use technology for teaching. 40% teachers took training but not from govt. institution. They took very simple training from private institution. Some of the teachers depicted that sometimes these trainings are not at all supportive. In statement 5, the report proves that all the teachers encourage their learners to use technology for it is effective to be adroit in EFL speaking. In statement 6, some of the teachers (30%) said that using technology is enough for teaching spoken English. On the contrary, 70% teachers said that only technology is not enough for teaching spoken English. Practical teaching is also important.

5.2 Results of Interview

The interview results depict the opinion of the respondents regarding different aspects of using technology for teaching EFL speaking. The teacher-participants were asked to provide their opinions in those aspects.

5.2.1 Tactics of Using Technology

The teacher-participants exposed their tactics to use technology in the classroom for EFL speaking and the report appeared is mentioned below:

Practice orally in the class	Using computer, mobile, projector (Audio-visual)	Using books	Real life situation practice
10%	35%	25%	30%

10% teachers make practice in the class orally, it is seen that 35% teachers use computer, mobile, projector. 25% teachers use books in order to teach English language. The teachers inform me that they are trying to improve their teaching, 30% teachers are teaching by practicing real life situation.

5.2.2 Effectiveness of using technology for teaching EFL speaking

The pie chart elucidates that 60% teachers considered technology as more effective than other ways. 35% teachers think it as an average way. About the technology use only 5% teachers told that it is little effective. It can be said definitely that the teachers of our country are improving to use technology. They have also got benefit to teach spoken English to the intermediate learners by using technology. About 60% teachers think that the perspective of 2018, is the age of computer which is very effective to teach English. 35% teachers thought it as medium because sometimes it hampers the students. Some teachers argue that it is very little effective because all student doesn't have mobile, computers, tab etc. but everybody agreed that it is not same effective.

5.2.3 Using technology is more effective than other ways of EFL speaking skill

Asking to the teachers about their opinion, the researcher found that 70% teachers agreed strongly, 25% agreed and only 5% teachers disagreed with the opinion that technology is more effective than other ways. We are at the postmodern age; the people of Bangladesh are improving to use technology. The students are very fond of using computers, mobile phones, internet, and media players. They can use the devices very eagerly and they may practice spoken English very easily. The teachers think that technology can enhance teaching efficacy for speaking skill that

matches Akter’s (2019) study that proved that short feature films can increase teaching effectiveness in the language classroom.

5.2.4 The Purpose of Using Technology in the Class

The pie chart presents that the purpose of using technology in the class for teaching spoken English. For the cause of downloading materials 50% teachers use technology in the class. For teaching spoken English, 25% teachers play video for showing video tutorial and video conversations 15% for listening and 10% use for browsing various sites.

According to the participants’ response, most of the teachers use technology for downloading materials to provide the students. Showing videos is also found very important to teach and learn spoken English. The quarter part of the teachers uses technology for showing videos to the students. Listening is the first condition of learning a language. 15 % teachers use audio for teaching spoken English in the class. 10 % is used for browsing various sites it may be learning or teaching or getting entertainment.

5.2.5 Problems of Intermediate Level Teachers Facing During Teaching EFL Speaking Through Technology

The pie chart shows that in the case of cost prohibition 35% teachers face problems by using technology in the class. 30% teachers said about the various problems of internet connection. 20% quandaries are found technical and electrical while 15% teachers are unable to use new technologies. According to the survey, the teachers said that most of the students come from very poor family they can’t pay more. In that case, most of the teachers face economical problem to carry the classes using technology. 30% of teachers said their colleges don’t provide regular access to the internet for students. During class time 20% teachers face electrical problem to use technology or in the middle time of the class Load shedding is occurred. Other most important problems are 15% teachers face unable to understand new technologies.

5.2.6 Teaching environment at the College

The pie chart explains that the environment at the college of teaching spoken English. Asking to the teachers about it, 35% teachers said that they use technology and oral practice in the class. Only 10% teachers teach orally in the class. 30% teachers teach making real life situation in the class. 25% teachers teach by using books. In comparison, technology and oral practice are done more than other ways in the class for language teaching. According to huge number of teachers, real life situation teaching system is better but the students are very fond of technology for learning English.

5.2.7 The hours of technology use in a week

The pie chart shows that 30% teachers use technology 7-8 hours for teaching EFL speaking at the college level. 20% teachers use technology minimum 3-4 hours. 9-10 hours are used by the 25% teachers, another 25% teachers use 5-6 hours for teaching spoken English. Among 100 technology user teachers 30% teachers use seven to eight hours for teaching English language. Other teachers also use technology but they do not spend adequate time on technology. Some teachers opined that they are trying to learn the use of technology.

5.2.8 Use of device for teaching spoken English to the HSC level Students

Asking about the use of technology for teaching spoken English to the HSC level students, 90% teachers use computer for teaching and 10% teachers don't use computer. 60% teachers play video/movie for teaching spoken English. 75% teachers use mobile software. 80% teachers play audio to improve student's listening power. 40% teachers open a chat group to practice English. But 80% teacher use internet for the purpose of teaching. The lowest number of teachers, 5% teachers uses radio for teaching in Bangladesh.

Computer is now available to the people of Bangladesh; the teachers use computer more than other devices. But it can be seen on survey that using mobile phone is not less than other about computer.

Some teachers don't use computer or Mobile but they use audio player for teaching English. Internet is used for collecting materials for teaching spoken English.

5.2.9 Budget on technology

The respondents were asked if there is any budget on technology at their institutions. 80% teachers responded 'yes' and 20% teachers said that they prefer to get such a budget but they can't. Comparing to others we can't get huge opportunities to use technologies. These 80% teachers are using technology which is very poor devices and other doesn't get but they prefer to use technology in the case of teaching spoken English.

6. RECOMMENDATION

At the age of satellite, the teachers should use technology for teaching EFL speaking to the HSC level students. The pedagogical instruction in the HSC level students should learn some lessons. In other words, EFL teachers should take training to become perfect to teach using technology. Secondly, from the analysis of the responses it is found that the participants are hardly participate in any training program to conduct technologically advanced classroom and most of the teachers realized that they need to take training to get best outcome from their teaching.

Ivy (2011) stated that, "there are no training schemes for language teachers to learn the use of whatever technology there might be. Teachers are expected to know these already or get help

from their colleagues” (p.207). The teachers may suggest watching English movies with subtitle which may help to the students. In the hall room, with some friends the students may watch English movies and teachers may ask some dialogues. The students will be motivated and they will learn with pleasure. However, Maniruzzaman (2008) suggested that Computer-assisted language learning or CALL can be applied for encouraging autonomous learning. In this way, learners can find out their own errors and mistakes, and check the segmental and supra segmental graphic representations. Teachers can use this method for showing the visual image of the sounds and symbols which can be very motivating.

7. CONCLUSION

The latest advances in computer technology have been providing higher secondary learners with innovative opportunities to develop each one of the four English language skills beyond the classroom’s walls. The new technology provides student’s with autonomy to learn on their own time and anywhere. The teachers can teach the students English language very easily through the proper use of technology. The teachers are facing some problems during teaching by using technology. The language teachers should be trained with a view to teaching effectively as well as the teachers should be active respecting using technology. It is considered by the teachers that technology-based classes are organized as well as well- planned which can be applied several times in several classes. It is found that most of the teachers and students use mobile, computer and browse internet as a result teaching material can be distributed among the students easily. The finding of the study recommends that technology-based language teaching is preferable in everywhere of Bangladesh.

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